

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Scopus || Electronic journal specializing in Scopus

ISSUE 3

 Acceptance of papers **MARCH, 2025**

Acceptance of papers
Published monthly

Topics
economics,
technology, social sciences

ISSN 3060-5229

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JOURNAL "INNOVATION SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY" HAS BEEN REGISTERED
UNDER THE NUMBER **C-5669633** BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS
COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE
FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

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AN OVERVIEW OF PROMISING ECONOMIC SECTORS SUPPORTED BY GREEN BOND FINANCING

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Abstract: In the context of the global shift toward sustainable development, green bonds are emerging as a crucial mechanism for financing environmentally focused projects. This article explores promising economic sectors that can attract investment through green bond issuance. The key sectors include renewable energy, eco-friendly transportation, energy-efficient construction, water resource management, green industries, sustainable agriculture, as well as waste recycling and the advancement of a circular economy.

The analysis highlights the impact of these financial instruments on sustainable economic growth, the reduction of carbon emissions, and the enhancement of resource efficiency. Particular attention is given to the role of the government in promoting green bond issuance and attracting institutional investors. The conclusions emphasize the necessity of further developing sustainable financing mechanisms to ensure environmental security and achieve long-term sustainability goals.

Key words: Green bonds, sustainable development, environmental projects, renewable energy, environmentally friendly transport, energy-efficient construction, water resource management, green industry, sustainable agro-industrial complex, waste recycling, circular economy, carbon emission reduction, resource efficiency, sustainable economic growth, institutional investors, government incentives, sustainable financing, environmental security.

INTRODUCTION

Green bonds are a relatively new source of financing and should be regarded as an innovative financial instrument. They serve as a means of investing in environmentally safe and resource-efficient technologies, as well as various programs and projects aimed at environmental protection, the development of the green economy, and the rational use of natural resources. Green bonds represent a promising additional financing mechanism for Uzbekistan’s environmentally sustainable transition. They are particularly relevant for supporting market-driven projects in renewable energy production and other highly cost-effective sectors. Given global trends in sustainable finance, the increasing demand for environmentally focused financial instruments, and mandatory climate risk disclosure requirements in several countries, Uzbek issuers have the opportunity to expand their investor base. Raising capital through green bond issuance will contribute to achieving national objectives within the transition process.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The term “green economy” first appeared in 1989 in the report *Blueprint for a Green Economy*, prepared for the UK government by a group of leading environmental economists David Pearce, Edward Barbier, and Anil Markandya. However, to this day, there is no universally accepted and strictly defined interpretation of this concept. The most widely recognized and frequently used definition of the green economy is provided by the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). According to UNEP, a green economy is “an economic system that enhances human well-being and ensures social equity while significantly reducing environmental risks and the depletion of natural resources”[1].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The green economy also encompasses the development, production, and application of technologies and equipment aimed at reducing pollutant emissions, as well as monitoring and forecasting climate change. Additionally, it actively promotes energy- and resource-efficient technologies, along with renewable energy sources (RES) [2].

In recent years, the transition to a green economy has become an essential component of the country's key strategic documents. Notably, it is reflected in The Strategy for the Development of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026 [3] and The Strategy for the Transition to a Green Economy for 2019–2030 [4]. The study employed both theoretical and empirical methods. The theoretical component included the analysis and synthesis of scientific literature, a review of contemporary research on the topic, and a comparative analysis of existing concepts.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

To assess the demand for green bond issuances, it is essential to examine the current state of the market:

Table 1. Analysis of Green Bond Issuers¹.

No	Issuers	Interest Rate (%)	Issuance Volume (USD million)	Maturity Period	Issuance Date
1	Ministries of Economy and Finance	16,25	328,2	3 Years 5 Years	October 2023
2	SAIPRO GROUP	Not Disclosed	4	5 Years	December 2023
3	SQB	Not Disclosed	10	5 Years	August 2023
4	Uzbekistan Mortgage Refinancing Company	18 %	3,86	5 Years	September 2024

The market for green bonds in Uzbekistan is actively developing, with issuances from both government and private organizations. Interest rates vary: government bonds offer 16.25%, while CFI bonds provide 18%. The interest rates of private companies are not disclosed, which may indicate confidential placement terms. The maturity period is generally five years for most issuances, except for government bonds, which also include three-year options. Issuance volumes range from 50 billion UZS (CFI) to 4.25 trillion UZS (government) and 100 million USD (SQB).

The issuers listed in the table have different objectives for issuing green bonds. For example, the bonds issued by the Ministry of Economy and Finance were placed on the London Stock Exchange, making them the first such bonds in the CIS. The funds raised are allocated to financing environmental projects, including the implementation of water-saving technologies and the development of railway transport.

The proceeds from the issuance of SAIPRO GROUP bonds will be directed towards the environmentally sustainable construction of the “Green Hills Resort,” including the use of renewable energy sources and waste management systems.

The funds raised from the issuance of green bonds by JSC SQB will be allocated to financing projects aimed at improving energy efficiency and developing renewable energy sources.

Similarly, the proceeds from the issuance of such bonds by CFI were used for building modernization projects incorporating energy-efficient technologies.

One of the key advantages of green bonds is their high level of reliability, as reflected in the credit ratings assigned to them. Issuers view these high ratings as a significant competitive advantage, as they enhance the attractiveness of securities among investors and provide access to more favorable financing terms. According to data from the Climate Bonds Initiative (CBI), in 2014, a significant portion of bonds with a green label received high credit ratings: 45% of such securities were rated A3, while another 16% were rated A2.

Notably, a high level of reliability is characteristic not only of bonds officially labeled as “green” but also of a broader segment of so-called “climate” bonds that lack formal certification. This factor is largely driven by extensive government support for the issuance of such financial instruments, including various incentive measures at the international level.

¹ The table was compiled by the author using economic literature

Thanks to these efforts, the investment appeal of climate bonds remains high, and their market capitalization continues to grow. As of mid-2015, the total volume of outstanding climate bonds with an investment rating above BBB reached \$266.3 billion. Notably, two-thirds of this amount accounted for bonds with ratings of A, A2, and A3, underscoring the high level of investor confidence in this asset class.

Table 2. Volumes of green bonds by credit rating in 2015 (\$ billion)².

Sector	AAA	AA	A	BBB
Water Resources	0	1	0	0
Emission Control in the Environment	0	0	0	2
Agriculture and Forestry	0	0	0	0
Construction and Industry	0,4	1,6	2,9	6,5
Multi-Sector	18,2	1,8	1	5
Energy	5,6	3	25,5	13,2
Transport	45,9	72	18	47,2

The analysis of the presented data reveals significant differences in the distribution of climate bonds across economic sectors, depending on their credit ratings:

Leading role of the transport sector. The transport sector holds the largest share of bonds, particularly in the AA (72) and BBB (47.2) categories. High ratings indicate a significant level of investor confidence, likely due to government initiatives and the long-term sustainability of infrastructure projects.

Energy as a key sector for green financing. In the A category (25.5), the energy sector ranks second, highlighting its strong investment appeal. However, the low volumes in AAA and AA may indicate certain risks related to technological and regulatory uncertainties.

Multi-sector representation in high-rated bonds. The multi-sector category is primarily represented in AAA (18.2), but its share drops sharply in lower ratings. This may suggest a high concentration of large, stable projects with strong creditworthiness.

Construction and industry with relatively low figures. Construction and industry show comparatively low values across all categories, possibly due to the high risks associated with long-term investments in this sector.

Absence of agriculture and forestry. Agriculture and forestry are entirely absent from the analyzed rating categories, which may indicate a lack of investment or the perception of these sectors as high-risk for green bond financing.

Emission control receives limited investment attention. The emission control sector is only represented in the BBB rating category (2), indicating insufficient investor attention to this area. Limited presence of water resources. Water resources have a minimal presence in the AA category (1), which may suggest the sector's specific characteristics make it less attractive for investors.

The obtained data confirm that the transport and energy sectors are the primary recipients of climate bond investments. High credit ratings in these sectors indicate significant investor confidence, likely driven by government support and the long-term stability of infrastructure projects. At the same time, agriculture and forestry, emission control, and water resources remain underfunded. This highlights the need to develop additional investment mechanisms to stimulate sustainable development in these sectors.

Based on the analyzed data, it is possible to make a cautious forecast regarding potentially promising investment areas. The energy sector in Uzbekistan, where natural gas currently holds a dominant position, is gradually becoming more attractive to investors in renewable energy sources. This trend is largely influenced by government support measures and the introduction of incentive programs. By 2030, the country aims to further diversify its electricity generation by increasing the share of solar photovoltaic power plants to 8% and expanding wind energy production. The data confirm that the transport and energy sectors are the primary recipients of green bond financing. High credit ratings in these industries indicate significant investor confidence, likely driven by government support and the long-term stability of infrastructure projects. At the same time, agriculture and forestry, emission control, and water resource management receive minimal investment, suggesting limited financial attractiveness or underdeveloped funding mechanisms in these sectors.

Based on the analyzed data, there is a moderate likelihood of identifying promising economic sectors for future green bond issuance in our country.

² The table was prepared by the author using statistics from the C-Bonds website

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Uzbekistan's energy sector, where natural gas currently holds a dominant position, is gradually becoming more attractive to renewable energy investors. This trend is largely driven by government support measures and the implementation of incentive programs. By 2030, the country aims to further diversify its electricity generation by increasing the share of solar photovoltaic power plants to 8% and wind power stations to 7%.

Furthermore, amid the sustainable development strategy for the transport sector, the Uzbek government has identified localized production and integration of electric vehicles into the country's transportation infrastructure as a key priority. UzAuto Motors, one of the two state-owned enterprises that have issued bonds in Uzbekistan, along with other companies, could leverage green bond issuance mechanisms to finance projects in the electric vehicle sector. This would not only support the environmental modernization of the industry but also help diversify financial instruments for capital raising.

Sustainable Financing for Uzbekistan's Agricultural Sector

Uzbekistan's agricultural sector plays a crucial role in employment and economic development, contributing significantly to the country's food security and exports. However, the industry faces major environmental challenges, including the need for water resource optimization and biodiversity conservation. Addressing these issues could be partially financed through the issuance of green bonds.

Investments in modernizing water supply systems, which currently rely on inefficient infrastructure such as dams, canals, and pumping stations, could align with green financing criteria. Projects focused on improving irrigation efficiency, water resource management, and waste recycling may qualify for inclusion in green bond issuances initiated by government agencies, financial institutions, and relevant corporate entities.

As part of its first issuance of sovereign bonds aimed at achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Uzbekistan has already integrated several initiatives related to modernizing its water management systems.

Moving forward, similar mechanisms could be applied to the issuance of sub-sovereign bonds, enabling regional and municipal authorities to attract capital for water resource management initiatives. However, the successful implementation of this approach will require regulatory and legislative adjustments, including addressing state borrowing regulations, aligning investment projects with environmental standards, and ensuring transparency in financing mechanisms.

References:

1. Why does green economy matter? [Electronic resource] // World Economic Forum. – Available at: <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/why-does-green-economy-matter>.
2. Kucherov A.V., Shibileva O.V. The Concept of the "Green" Economy: Key Provisions and Development Prospects // Young Scientist. 2014. No. 4. Pp. 561-563.
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-60 "On the Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan", dated 28.01.2022.
4. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4477 "On the Approval of the Strategy for the Transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a 'Green' Economy for the Period 2019-2030", dated 04.10.2019.
5. Jonson, E. The Complete Guide to National Climate-Related Disclosures, Carbon Cloud, (2022).
6. What is green finance and why is it important? [Electronic resource] // World Economic Forum. – Nov. 2022. – Available at: <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2022/11/why-does-green-economy-matter/> – Accessed: 30.08.2022.
7. Green Swan Conference 2022 [Electronic resource] // The Bank for International Settlements. – Available at: https://www.bis.org/events/green_swan_2022/overview.htm – Accessed: 01.09.2022.
8. <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/journal>

Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2025. № 3

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